

Assessment on the Level of Implementation of Environmental Laws in the Philippines

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Abstract:- Protecting the natural environment may seem overwhelming with increased natural disasters. The continuous exploration of natural resources contributes to the destructive effects of natural calamities, resulting in loss of lives, destruction of properties and environment. The main aimed of this paper is to determine the level implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws of in camarines sur, Philippines. This study was used survey method of research to assess the implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines. the data collected through survey and Focus Group Discussions(FGD) Informant Key Interview (KII).Finding reveals that the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines with an overall average weighted mean 3.145 interpreted as moderately implemented and they experienced challenges during the implementations. Conclusions that the environmental laws were moderately implemented and effective although there are challenges during the implementations. Hence, future researchers may conduct follow up research to generatenew knowledge for policy implementations.

Keywords: *assessment, level of implementation, environmental laws in the Philippines.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The environmental issues have been the growing concerned in the past decades in the sense that several policies propounded by advocates of environmental protection have been realized all over the world. However, the continuing activities involving corrupt politicians and other government official that protect the illegal activities committed by the violators of environmental laws of the country, definitely, it will causes environmental degradation. (INTERPOL-UNEP report 2016). The development of the country and the continuous industrialization as part of the growing economy there is a human impacts to the environment that why environmental issues have been the concerned all over the world. Priyanka Yadav, Vishal Mishra (2021). The challenges to the government and law enforcement agency on the implementation of environmental is on how to eradicate the criminal offenders and bring it before the court in order answer the legal consequence of his/her acts. Because some country will not prioritizing environmental crimes. Hence , there is a widespread of law violators due to lack of implementation and proper enforcement to address the issue of environmental challenges.(UNEDP-Global assessment Report 2016) the environment criminology and other social scientist define the value of environmental crimes that

affects the daily lives of every citizens including the socioeconomic dependency that rely on the issue on how to deal with it. And the identified issue relating to environment the certain government tend to address and provide a program that will compensate the effects of this global concerned.

The effective implementation of environmental laws and regulations become a variety of concern in order to regulate the proper utilization of natural resource for sustainable development and for future generations Saharamki, L. Kankaanranta, T.T. (2021). The crime involving environmental concerned come to the attention of the global leaders and advocates due to serious deleterious impact to the natural resources and also to peace, security and development (A UNEP- INTERPOL Rapid Response Assessment Report 2016). The significant problem nowadays is the rapidly growing significant environmental issues that have not been properly addressed Priyanka Yadav, Vishal Mishra (2021). The governance policy implemented by the government must be on the general welfare of the people as a whole, although the government acts as parents state still there is a need to acts judiciously in all dealing with the people Gera, W. (2016). When there is an active cooperation amongst community members and other stakeholders the implementation of environmental laws becomes effective Marcial, M. et .al. (2016) due to intense tropical storms climatic disturbances, destructive heavy rains and repetitive floods the natural and built environments are under threat globally. Priyanka Yadav, Vishal Mishra (2021). The prevailing tensions and power imbalances between government and the private sector, this may results to arbitrary policy that compromises in perpetual square-off against the local and foreign investors. Gera, W. (2016) However, the ambivalent framework of governance that will not be determined its priority the government should reconcile misleading interests in the business industry W. (2016) in order to achieve the objective of highly eco-efficiency in different sectors of the economy sustainable development strategy of the country Priyanka Yadav, Vishal Mishra (2021)

The Philippines is an archipelagic country wherein the issue on environment crimes is an innermost concerned of the government and the environmental advocates. However, there is still a continuing illegal activities occur in different part of the country that cannot be address due to limited number human resources. That is why the illegal logging activities, small scale mining, illicit trafficking in wildlife, and illegal, unregulated, and unreported fishing, have broader impacts. That threaten the food security by

depleting fish stocks, forest and other resources and resulting to an impending economic development and reducing revenue. Under the Philippine constitution, it is the duty of the government to protect and advance the rights of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature; (Article II, section 6, of the 1987 Philippine Constitution) And the communities' have the right to access the natural resource and the government should provide a livelihood program ensure the economic sustainability country Guiang, E. S, et al(2001).Illegal logging is a threat to biodiversity and rural livelihoods Van der Ploeg et, al (2011). illicit trade in rare ornamental plant species, the country's illegal online plant trade has increased in recent years. (Global Organized Crime Index Report 2021). The problems resulting from environmental pollution indicate people's inability to manage local problems over external issues Priyanka Yadav, Vishal Mishra (2021). Strengthening implementation of environmental laws and controlling corruption are prerequisites for sustainable forest management Van der Ploeg et, al (2011).This trends encourage the researcher conduct this study to assess the implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines. and provide recommendation to further enhance the implementation of environmental laws. And identify the gaps in the implementation of environmental laws in camarines Sur.

- **Purpose of this Study:** The objectives of this study is to determine the level implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in the Philippines. Specifically, it answer the following specific questions; What are the environmental laws implemented in the Philippines? What is the level of implementation of environmental laws ?What are the challenges during Implementation of environmental laws ?

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Sites

This study conducted in the province of camarines sur. Camarines Sur is a province in the Philippines situated in the Bicol Region occupying the southeastern peninsula of Luzon and the outlying island provinces of Masbate and Catanduanes. Its capital is the Municipality of Pili. The province has a land area of 5,511.90 square kilometers or 2,128.16 square miles. Its population as determined by the 2020 Census was 2,068,244. This represented 34.01% of the total population of the Bicol Region, 3.33% of the overall population of the Luzon island group, or 1.90% of the entire population of the Philippines. Based on these figures, the population density is computed at 375 inhabitants per square kilometer or 972 inhabitants per square mile.

Fig. 1: Map of Camarines Sur

Source: <https://www.mapsofworld.com/philippines/provinces/camarines-sur.html>

The following are the respondents of the study; the monitoring and enforcement section - Department of Environment and Natural Resources (MES- DENR) members of the (Bantay Kalikasan) selected Barangay Officials and selected members of the community in camarines sur.

Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study. A letter permissions will be sought to the concern

officials such as; Community Environment and Natural Resources Office – Monitoring and Enforcement Section, Bantay kalikasan, Barangay Captain, sanguniang bayan members community member and the like. Due to IATF Omnibus Rules in the observance of health protocols under pandemic. The researcher with the help of the subject unit will identify the target interviewee participants.

B. Research Design

This study employed mixed methods of research to assess the implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines. Respondents of this study selected through convenient sampling and the data collected through survey and Focus Group Discussions (FGD In formant Key Interview (KII). This method used to determine the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in camarines sur. identify the challenges encountered along Implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur.

C. Instrument and data Collection

The instrument , aFour(4)point Liker scales to determine the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in the Province of Camarines Sur, Philippines.And athematic analysis to present the data to determine the challenges during the implementation of environmental laws in the study sites.

D. Treatment of Data

The data gathered will be analyze with descriptive statistical techniques for quantitative data and thematic analysis for the qualitative data.

III. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Summary of Environmental Laws in the Philippines

Environmental laws this pertains to laws, executive order, ordinances, letter of instructions, implementing rules and regulations and customary laws that address the effects of human activity on the natural environmentanda variety of protections which share the goal of protecting the environment. It is also referred to as laws enacted intended to protect and preserved our natural resources for public interest and for sustainable environmental economic security.The Philippines is a diverse country with rich ecosystems that serve as habitats of endemic species of flora and fauna and the natural resources, however, environmental changes brought about by exploitation such as poaching, deforestation, land degradation through conversion for other usage, climate change and pollution.

In the summary of environmental laws implemented in the Philippines and the provisions of the related laws were presented in Table 1 below:

No	Environmental Laws
1	Presidential Decree No. 1586- Philippine Environmental Impact statement System
2	Presidential Decree No.705- Revised Forestry Code of the Philippines
3	Republic Act No. 9175-Chain Saw Act of 2005
4	Republic Act No. 7586- National Integrated Protected Areas system Act of 1992,
5	Republic Act No.7942-Philippine Mining Act of 1995
6	Republic Act No.8749-Philippine Clear Air Act of 1999
7	Republic Act No.9003- Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000,
8	Republic Act No.9275-Philippine Clear Water Act of 2004
9	Republic Act No. 6969- Toxic and Hazardous Substance and Nuclear Waste Control Act of 1990
10	Republic Act No.9147- Wild Life Act.
11	Other related laws

Table 1: Summary of Environmental Laws Philippines

Source: DENR Administrative Order No. 2008-01- February 06, 2008 Section 2.

In table 1 presented the summary of the environmental laws implemented in the Philippines. Such as the Presidential Decree No. 1586- Philippine Environmental Impact Statement System wherein the main objectives of this law to assure the public that environmental issue would be considered in the decision making process before the implementation of the projects, to determined the adverse effects of the proposed projects are anticipated, avoided or offset.Environmental Impact Assessment(EIA) also ensures the communities the proper utilization of natural resources and the ecological process are protected. The input of the communities and stakeholders willalso considered for the development process of the proposed project. EIA is necessary in order to predict, evaluate and mitigate the biophysical, social and relevant socio-economic effects on the development propose or activities before decision are being made for their approval.Presidential Decree No. 705 otherwise known as the forestry reform code of the Philippines.Thepurpose of this law is to regulate the multiple uses of forest landsclassifications, survey, establishment of wood-processing plants, the protection,

development and rehabilitation of forest lands to ensure their continuity in productive condition.Republic Act No. 9175Otherwise known as the "Chain Saw Act of 2002This law aimed to regulate the ownership, possession, sale, importation and use of chain saws,to prevent them from being used in illegal logging or unauthorized clearing of forests and provide penalties for violations of this act.

The Republic Act No. 7586this act shall be known and referred to as the "National Integrated Protected Areas System Act of 1992 the purpose of this law is to regulate the human activities on all components of the natural environment due to the effect of increasing population, resource exploitation and industrial advancement and recognizing the critical importance of protecting and maintaining the natural biological and physical diversities of the environment notably on areas with biologically unique features to sustain human life and development, as well as plant and animal life.This law was also preservethe distinct features that posses common ecological values that may be incorporated into a holistic plan representative of our natural

heritage; that effective administration of this area is possible only through cooperation among national government, local government and concerned private organizations, that the use and enjoyment of these protected areas must be consistent with the principles of biological diversity and sustainable development.

Republic Act No. 6969 known as Toxic and Hazardous Substance and Nuclear Waste Control Act of 1990 the main aim of this law to regulate, restrict or prohibit the importation, manufacture, processing, sale, distribution, use and disposal of chemical substances and mixtures. It shall also include to keep inventory, monitor and regulate, inform and educate the populace regarding the hazard and risk and prevent the entry of chemicals or even in transit as well as storage and disposal of hazardous waste within the territorial limits of the country for whatever purpose.

Republic Act No. 7942 March 3, 1995. This act instituting a new system of mineral resources exploration, development, utilization, and conservation. Wherein the government policy that all mineral resources in public and private lands within the territory and exclusive economic zone of the Republic of the Philippines are owned by the State. And it is also the responsibility of the State to promote their rational exploration, development, utilization and conservation through the combined efforts of government and the private sector in order to enhance national growth in a way that effectively safeguards the environment and protect the rights of affected communities. Consequently, mineral resources are owned by the State and the exploration, development, utilization, and processing thereof shall be under its full control and supervision of the government. And the state may directly undertake such activities or it may enter into mineral agreements with contractors. The State shall recognize and protect the rights of the indigenous cultural communities to their ancestral lands as provided for by the Constitution.

Republic Act No. 8749 June 23, 1999 otherwise known as Philippine Clean Air Act of 1999. This act provides a comprehensive air pollution control policy, protect and advance the right of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature. Promote and protect the global environment to attain sustainable development while recognizing the primary responsibility of local government units to deal with environmental problems. Recognize the responsibility of cleaning the habitat and environment as primarily area-based. Also recognizes the principle that "polluters must pay". Finally, the State recognizes that a clean and healthy environment is for the good of all and should, therefore, be the concern of all.

Republic Act No. 9003 this act provides for an ecological solid waste management program, and created institutional mechanisms and incentives, declaring certain acts prohibited and providing penalties. This Act shall be known as the "Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000." This act ensures the protection of public health and environment, proper utilization of valuable resources and encourages resource conservation and recovery, create

guidelines for waste generation and reduction measures through waste minimization including composting, recycling, re-use, recovery, green charcoal process, and others, before collection, treatment and disposal in appropriate and environmentally sound solid waste management facilities in accordance with ecologically sustainable development principles, encourage research and development programs to improve solid waste management and conservation efforts. Encourage the participation of all stakeholders to participate in the development and implementation of comprehensive and ecological solid waste management program.

Republic Act No. 9147 This Act shall be known as the "Wildlife Resources Conservation and Protection Act of 2001." This act shall be applicable for all wildlife species found in all areas of the country, including exotic species which are subject to trade, cultured, maintained and/or bred in captivity or propagated. The objectives of this law is to conserve and protect wildlife species and their habitats and promote ecological balance and enhance biological diversity, and regulate the collection and trade of wildlife to pursue the national interest that the Philippines is committed to international conventions, protection of wildlife and their habitats, and initiate support to scientific studies on the conservation of biological diversity.

Table 1 shows that majority of the environmental laws implemented in the Philippines formulated in the House of Representatives and Senate of the Philippines. Interestingly, these policies were implemented by local government units (LGU), which are under the umbrella of the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG). Wherein the concerned government agency regarding the implementation of environmental laws were the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) and other government agencies. Consequently, there is no clear strategic framework as to the implementation of environmental law in the country. When the interests of the national government and the local ones are not unified, there will be distorted, boycott policy behavior in the policy implementation (Buchanan and Tollison (1984) as cited by Zhang, T., Yao, H. (2018)). On the other hand, it can be seen that there is a comprehensive environmental policy in the Philippines (World Bank (2009)). Absence of an independent monitoring mechanism with regards to the implementation of environmental policy these become ineffective. Also the implementation of environmental policies need more transparency. However, the mandates among different agencies is not very clear and sometimes there exist overlapping responsibilities and blank zones. Thus, it is inevitable that there will be conflicts of interests or the state of the edge of the unmanaged, which have weakened the effect in the implementation of environmental policies. Zhang, T., Yao, H. (2018)

B. Level of Implementation and effectiveness of Environmental Laws in Camarines Sur, Philippines

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents perceived knowledge on the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines. Data shows that the overall average weighted mean were 3.105 Interpreted as moderately implemented

and effective. Interestingly, Republic Act No.9275-Philippine Clear Water Act of 2004 and Republic Act No. 9175-Chain Saw Act of 2005,both highly implemented and effective. While the other laws enumerated under DENR Administrative Order No. 2008-01- February 06,2008 Section 2 were moderately implemented and effective.

No	Indicators	Implementation		Effectiveness	
		Value	Verbal Description	Value	Verbal Description
1	Presidential Decree No. 1586- Philippine Environmental Impact statement System	2.42	MI	2.46	ME
2	Presidential Decree No.705- Revised Forestry Code of the Philippines,	3.12	MI	3.21	ME
3	Republic Act No. 6969- Toxic and Hazardous Substance and Nuclear Waste Control Act of 1990,	3.09	MI	3.09	ME
4	Republic Act No. 7586- National Integrated Protected Areas system Act of 1992,	3.11	MI	3.11	ME
5	Republic Act No.7942-Philippine Mining Act of 1995,	2.92	MI	2.95	ME
6	Republic Act No.8749-Philippine Clear Air Act of 1999,	2.98	MI	2.98	ME
7	Republic Act No.9003- Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000,	3.08	MI	3.08	ME
8	Republic Act No.9275-Philippine Clear Water Act of 2004,	3.38	HI	3.42	HE
9	Republic Act No. 9175-Chain Saw Act of 2005,	3.42	HI	3.46	HE
10	Republic Act No.9147- Wild Life Act.	3.14	MI	3.19	ME
11	Other related laws	3.42	HI	3.46	HE
	Average Weighted Mean	3.09	MI	3.12	ME

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents perceived knowledge on the Level of Implementation and Effectiveness of Environmental Laws in Camarines Sur, Philippines

Source: DENR Administrative Order No. 2008-01- February 06,2008 Section 2

Legend:3.26-4.00 -Highly Implemented, 2.52-3.25 Moderately Implemented, 1.76-2.50 Less Implemented, 1.00-1.75 Not Implemented and 3.26-4.00 - Highly Effective, 2.52-3.25 - Moderately Effective, 1.76-2.50 - Less Effective, 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

The results implied that the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental law in the country were moderately, implemented despite the fact that the policies enacted at the house of representative and senate of the Philippines and there is limitation budget and human resources. World Bank (2009) to sustain the implementation of environmental there must be a strategic frameworks for cooperation under the Declaration of ASEAN Concord II, 2015. Kanokporn Swangjang (2018)the strategic frameworks towards the devolution of functions of national government to the local government unit must be presented to give clear picture and enhanced resource mobilization for environmental management, better prioritization, and retooling of human resources are urgently needed to accommodate new priorities. World Bank (2009)

C. Level of Implementation and Effectiveness of Environmental Laws in Camarines Sur, Philippines

The agency responsible for the implementation of environmental laws in the Philippines is the Department of Environment and Natural Resources(DENR) is the primary government agency responsible for the implementation and enforcement of this Act, with the support of other government organizations, local government units, non - government organizations and the private sector.

In this section the perceived knowledge on the strategies in the implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws was presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents perceived knowledge on the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in the province of camarines Sur. Data revealed that the overall area weighted mean were 3.145 interpreted as moderately implemented and effective. While the activities conducted awareness seminar/information campaign/ dialogue/lecture relevant to environmental crimes, and intensified border control measures to deny entry of suspected illegal activities

relating to environmental crime were 3.26 highly implemented and effective.

No	Indicators	Implementation		Effectiveness	
		Value	Verbal Description	Value	Verbal Description
1	Conducted Awareness Seminar/information Campaign/ Dialogue/lecture relevant to environmental crimes	3.42	HI	3.46	HE
2	Distributed IEC materials on relevant Environmental Laws	3.14	MI	3.17	ME
3	Established regular Task Force kalikasan Check Point	3.09	MI	3.09	ME
4	Conducted inspection on the establishment doing wood works and similar establishments	3.11	MI	3.11	ME
5	Deploy officers in the environmental protected areas and Other Public Areas such as Port , Terminals and other place of convergence(Task Force Visibility Presence)	2.92	MI	2.92	ME
6	Conduct systematic search for illegal activity in suspected prone areas	2.98	MI	2.98	ME
7	Strictly implement environmental laws and other related illegal activities	3.08	MI	3.08	ME
8	Intensified border control measures to deny entry of suspected illegal activities relating to environmental crime	3.38	HI	3.42	HE
	Average Weighted Mean	3.14	MI	3.15	ME

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents on the Perceived Knowledge on Strategies in the Level of Implementation and Effectiveness of Environmental Laws in Camarines Sur, Philippines

Legend:3.26-4.00 -Highly Implemented, 2.52-3.25 Moderately Implemented, 1.76-2.50 Less Implemented, 1.00-1.75 Not Implemented and 3.26-4.00 - Highly Effective, 2.52-3.25 - Moderately Effective, 1.76-2.50 - Less Effective, 1.00-1.75 - Not Effective

On the other hand distributed IEC materials on relevant environmental laws, established regular task force kalikasan check point, Conducted inspection on the establishment doing wood works and similar establishments, Deploy officers in the environmental protected areas and other public areas such as Port , Terminals and other place of convergence(Task Force Visibility Presence), Conduct systematic search for illegal activity in suspected prone areas, Strictly implement environmental laws and other related illegal activities were 3.05 moderately implemented and effective. Consequently, this result shows that the government agency involved in the implementation of environmental laws are complaints to their mandates.

D. Challenges along the Implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines

The implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur is a great challenge to the implementers such as the monitoring and enforcement unit of the different agencies, the law enforcers, the local government unit, the barangay official and etc. Since Camarines Sur is a province in the Philippines situated in the Bicol Region occupying the southeastern peninsula of Luzon and the outlying island provinces of Masbate and Catanduanes. The province has a land area of 5,511.90 square kilometers or 2,128.16 square miles. Its population as determined by the 2020 Census was 2,068,244. This represented 34.01% of the total population of the Bicol Region, 3.33% of the overall population of the Luzon island group, or 1.90% of the entire population of the Philippines. Based on these figures, the population density is computed at 375 inhabitants per square kilometer or 972 inhabitants per square mile.

In this part identified the challenges along the implementation of environmental laws likely presents the indicators components/descriptor in Table 4 below.

Challenges Along implementation	Indicator Component/ Descriptor
Political Intervention	Political Intervention Politics Partisan Politics
Policy and Governance	Fair/ Equitable Justice System Penalties
Human Resource and Finances	Need for Continuous Skills enhancement Training to level their Knowledge in the implementation and investigations
Public Relations and cooperation	Lack of community support Government agencies People's Organization Private Organizations and associations
Capacity/Capability	Limited number of personnel Resistance of the during the apprehension Lack of Training attended Lack of knowledge on environmental laws

Table 4: Challenges along Implementation of environmental laws in camarines sur, Philippines

A. Political Intervention

This involves in influencing or manipulating the legal actions of a politician or political party in any law enforcement agency of the government or any branches of criminal justice system in the Philippines that will hinder the implementing agency to prosecute the unscrupulous environmental or criminal law violators. It is also refers to an act beyond their jurisdiction in order to coerce or threat of force. The politics as we can see also influence the implementation of law of a country or other area, especially the debate or conflict among individuals or a political parties having or hoping to achieve power.

B. Policy and Governance

Public office is the public trust and every government employee is accountable to the people in his action according the KII. Hence, public policy generally also consists of the set of laws, memorandum, letter of instructions, circular, executive order adopted by a government. However, the issues brought draws the attention of the respondents concern with the new governance to the extent to which these actions are often performed now by agents of the state rather than directly by the state. Because the implementation of the policy and governance relating to environmental laws was not fair/equitable and the decision of the justice system are influence by top level position of the government. Hence, the right penalties shall not be implemented.

C. Human Resource and Finances

During the KII another challenges along the implementation is the human resources in the since that there is a limited number of personnel in-charge in the enforcement and monitoring of environmental laws and the local level there is aneed for continuous skills enhancement training to level their knowledge in the implementation and investigations and prosecution of the law violators.

D. Public Relations and Cooperation

Public relations is the heart of every organization specially in the implementation of environmental laws. However, along with that based from the response of the respondents the weakness on the implementation of the said law were lack of community support and cooperation because some of the community members are no longer interested because even if they cooperate they to law enforcement agencies to strictly implement the law still the case will not pursue because of political intervention, while there is an existing memorandum of agreement with government agencies to protect natural resources, through the active participation of the different Civic Organization, Private Organizations and associations.

E. Capacity/Capability

The capacity of the implementers of environmental laws was not sufficient because of the limited number of personnel, and there were resistance of the suspect during the apprehension, and according to KII thelack of training attended and lack of knowledge of different environmental laws are the identified challenges along the implementations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of environment laws are the great challenge in every sovereign state on how to sustain the environmental climate for the country's development. Hence, the level of implementation and effectiveness of environmental laws in camarines sur , Philippines were moderately implemented despite the facts that majority of the laws implemented enacted at the House of Representative and senate of the Philippines while implemented in the local government unit. And also respondents identified the challenges during implementation of environmental laws.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In relation with the findings and conclusions of this research, the following are recommended: The community environment and natural resources –monitoring and enforcement unit and other law enforcement agency may deploy officers in the environmental protected areas and other public areas such as port , terminals and other place of convergence(Task Force Visibility Presence)to strictly implement environmental laws and other related illegal activities.conduct interagency coordination to identify violators of environmental laws.

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